

FE MODELING AND NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF FLOW-DEFORMATION PROCESSES IN COMPOSITES MANUFACTURING

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Abstract

In present work, we attempt to unify the modeling of different sub-processes under the umbrella of two-phase porous media theory. Two sub processes are considered: (1) the wetting and compaction of individual plies and (2) the overall preform deformation and macroscopic Darcian flow. The idea is to identify a set of relevant constituents, i.e. particles, voids and liquids, and assign them to pertinent media. The result is a set of overlapping continuous media, each having its own density-, velocity- and stress field on the macroscopic scale. In addition, we introduce internal variables to describe irreversible micro-processes in the system, such as microscopic infiltration and preform deformation. In this work we extend the previous developments, coupling the preform deformation on different scales to the process of micro infiltration, with respect to the modeling of the micro-compaction as well as the Darcian interaction on the macro scale. A coupled displacement-pressure, geometrically non-linear, finite element model is presented. The approach is applied to a representative numerical example where we used parameter values out of the literature and estimates from our own micrographs.

1 Introduction

Traditional processing of high quality composite materials requires autoclave consolidation and curing at elevated pressure and temperature. Composite parts cured inside an autoclave have excellent quality; however, this quality comes with a high price tag. Recent developments in prepreg technology have led to the development of an Out-Of-Autoclave (OOA) prepreg that can be cured with only vacuum pressure and lower temperatures [1]. Vacuum Bag Only (VBO) prepreps are a member of the family of OOA techniques for composite manufacturing in which composite laminates are produced from prepreps by vacuum-bag

consolidation followed by curing in an oven [2]. The advantages of VBO over autoclave processing are lower capital investment, elimination of the need for costly nitrogen gas, greater energy efficiency and reduction of size constraints (larger parts) [3].

The modeling and simulation of composites manufacturing require a series of sub-models describing the relevant mechanisms. Moreover, the modeling requires a unifying continuum mechanical umbrella in order to handle all the sub-models simultaneously, while ensuring positive energy dissipation under the invariance of mass balance and balances of momentum and energy. Some of the necessary sub-models already exist, describing permeability of arrays of fibers, infiltration of a fiber bundle, elasticity of fiber packing etc., and may be generalized to constitutive equations and applied in a continuum context. As to the continuum formulation a few researchers, e.g. Larsson et al. [4], Pillai et al. [5], Li and Tucker [6], have proposed formulations to predict the consolidation as a function of coupled flow and deformation-based two-phase porous media theory, cf. also [7] for a review of recent developments related to large deformation consolidation modeling.

The purpose of the present work is to extend the developments in [4] concerning two-phase continuum model for preform elasticity and wetting towards a more general formulation including macroscopic anisotropic resin flow. A more general anisotropic model for the wetted preform is also proposed. Like in the previous formulation, a particular concern is the modeling of solid compressibility due to meso-level wetting of the preform. In this context, another approach is to formulate mass balance in terms of logarithmic compaction strain measures that may be used to specify the compressibility of the different phases via the entropy inequality, cf. Larsson and Larsson [7].

2 Homogenized theory of porous media

2.1 Micro constituents

To begin to build up the model we need to distinguish the constituents in different scales and the link between them. Three different micro constituents identified as follow where they satisfy the saturation constraint

$$\phi^p + \phi^l + \phi^v = 1. \quad (1)$$

- Incompressible solid particles, p , with the volume fraction $\phi^p = V^p/V$, representing the fibers.
- Incompressible liquid constituent, l , with the volume fraction $\phi^l = V^l/V$, representing the resin.
- Voids, v , with the volume fraction $\phi^v = V^v/V$, embedded in the fiber plies.

We also relate to the two-phase porous media theory, where the micro-constituents are considered homogenized. In particular, the macroscopic volume fractions for the solid and the fluid phases, n^s and n^f , are defined as

$$n^s = \frac{V^s}{V}, \quad n^f = \frac{V^f}{V}. \quad (2)$$

In view of equation (1), we also have the saturation constraint

$$n^s + n^f = 1, \quad n^s = \phi^p + \phi^v, \quad n^f = \phi^l. \quad (3)$$

As to the modeling of fluid infiltration of fiber plies, the partially saturated fibers (named particles) are subdivided into a wet portion (already penetrated by resin fluid) and a dry portion. Hence, the fiber content in the dry region of the fiber bed is obtained as

$$\phi = (1 - \xi) \left(\frac{\rho^p}{\rho^s} - \xi \right)^{-1}. \quad (4)$$

It should be noted that, based on the formulation in [5], manipulation has been done to obtain equation (4) in terms of a saturation ratio ξ defining the degree of wet out within a representative fiber ply and also the densities of the solid portion and the particles. Based on equation (4) and the state of the saturation degree, ξ we are able to obtain the compaction of the solid phase as a function of irreversible wetting factor ξ and the reversible packing volume fraction ϕ in the form of additive decomposition of the total strain ε , cf. [8] for detail, as

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^p, \quad (5)$$

where the reversible compaction strain ε^e (related to the packing ϕ and the saturation degree ξ) and the irreversible wetting compaction ε^p (related only to the saturation degree ξ) are defined.

2.2 Governing equations

Assuming that the void motion is affine with the particle motion, the micro problem of three actual constituents in the mixture may be reduced to a two-phase continuum problem. We thereby focus our attention to the formulation of a binary continuum model, consisting of a compressible solid phase, s , and an incompressible fluid phase, f . Following the developments in [9] we model the problem using the following governing equations.

The total mass balance of our binary mixture to obtain the combined mass balance relation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^s - n^s \dot{\varepsilon} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^d, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{v}^d is the Darcian velocity defined from the relative velocity between phases $\mathbf{v}^r = \mathbf{v}^s - \mathbf{v}^f$ as $\mathbf{v}^d = n^f \mathbf{v}^r$, \mathbf{v}^s is the solid phase velocity and \mathbf{v}^f is the fluid phase velocity.

Considering the localized format of the momentum balance in the spatial format, we obtain the balance relation for quasi-static behavior of the mixture, corresponding to the total form of the momentum balance specified in [8] as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \nabla + \hat{\rho} \mathbf{g} = 0 \quad \forall x \in B, \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^s + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f$ is the total Cauchy stress, $\hat{\rho}$ is the bulk density, \mathbf{g} is the gravity and B represents the current configuration domain. In turn, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is related to the effective (constitutive) stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the fluid pressure p via the Terzaghi effective stress principle,

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - p \mathbf{1}. \quad (8)$$

In order to arrive at proper FE-formulation, we derive the weak form of the coupled set of equations (6) and (7). Whereby the mass balance is recast into weak form as

$$\int_{B_0} (\boldsymbol{\tau} - Jp\mathbf{1}) : l[\mathbf{w}] dV = \int_{\Gamma_0} \mathbf{w} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}}_1 d\Gamma \quad \forall \mathbf{w} \in P, \quad (9)$$

and momentum balance is recast into weak form becomes

$$\int_{B_0} \eta j dV - \int_{B_0} \eta n_0^s e^\epsilon \dot{\epsilon} dV - \int_{B_0} (\nabla \eta) \cdot J \mathbf{v}^d dV = - \int_{\Gamma_0} \eta Q d\Gamma \quad \forall \eta \in S, \quad (10)$$

where in turn P is the function space containing the virtual displacement field $\mathbf{w}[\mathbf{x}]$, and S is the function space containing the virtual fluid pressure field $\eta[\mathbf{x}]$. We also introduced prescribed tractions $\bar{\mathbf{t}} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ and flow $Q = \mathbf{v}^d \cdot \mathbf{n}$ on the outer surface Γ_0 . Throughout the FE analyses, a Taylor-Hood element is adopted corresponding to quadratic interpolation for the placement and linear interpolation for the fluid pressure. More detail is presented in section 3 for numerical procedure.

2.3 Balance of energy and entropy for isothermal behavior

A combined balance of energy yields the change of internal energy of the mixture material. Likewise, the entropy inequality for the mixture material is obtained pertinent to isothermal behavior which combined with the energy equation, cf. [8], yields

$$D = \underbrace{\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{l} - n^s p \dot{\epsilon} + \hat{\rho}^s \dot{\psi}^s}_{D^s} + \underbrace{\mathbf{v}^d \cdot (\rho^f \mathbf{g} - \nabla p)}_{D^i} \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

where ψ^s is the free energy for the solid phase, \mathbf{l} is the solid velocity gradient and p is the intrinsic fluid pressure. The total mechanical dissipation D is thus interpreted in terms of a few independent phenomenological mechanisms where $D^s \geq 0$ is the dissipation produced by the (homogenized) solid phase material considered as an independent process of the mixture. The contribution $D^i \geq 0$ represents dissipation induced by “drag”-interaction between the phases, where \mathbf{h}_e^f is the effective drag force.

2.4 Constitutive equations

Upon assuming hyper-elasticity of the effective stress response we obtain the dependence $\psi^s(\mathbf{C}, \epsilon, \epsilon^p)$ in the free energy for the solid phase. Considering the free energy in dissipation inequality we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\psi}(\mathbf{C}, \epsilon, \epsilon^p) &= \psi_{mac}(\mathbf{C}) + \psi_{mes}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p) = \\ &= \frac{\partial \psi_{mac}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \frac{\partial \psi_{mes}}{\partial \epsilon} \dot{\epsilon} + \frac{\partial \psi_{mes}}{\partial \epsilon^p} \dot{\epsilon}^p \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where we assumed an additive split of the free energy into macroscopic and mesoscopic parts.

Referring to the dissipation inequality and the final conclusion in (12) we arrive to the state equations

$$\mathbf{S} = 2\hat{\rho}_0^s \frac{\partial \psi_{mac}}{\partial \mathbf{C}}, \quad (13)$$

$$p = -\rho^s \frac{\partial \psi_{mes}}{\partial \epsilon}, \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{S} = \bar{\mathbf{S}} - J\mathbf{C}^{-1}p$ is the effective second Piola-Kirchhoff stress due to the Terzaghi effective stress principle. In the following we subdivide the stress response in terms of the effective fiber bed response considered hyperelastic governed by the stored energy function for Neo-Hooke like elastic material written as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{mac}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}, J) &= G(\mathbf{1} : \hat{\mathbf{C}} - 3) + J \frac{k^s E}{\beta - 1} \left(\frac{\phi_0^p}{J} \right)^\beta, \\ \hat{\mathbf{C}} &= J^{-\frac{2}{3}} \mathbf{F}^t \cdot \mathbf{F}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and the solid phase compaction associated with micro infiltration induced by fluid pressure:

$$p + p_0 = kE\phi^\alpha, \quad (16)$$

where the homogenized free energy is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{mes} &= \frac{p_0}{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^s} - \xi \frac{1}{\rho_0^s} \phi_0 \right) \left(\epsilon^\alpha - \alpha \log \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0^\alpha} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\rho_0^s} \frac{p_0}{\alpha} \frac{e^\epsilon - \phi_0}{1 - \alpha \phi_0} \left(\epsilon^\alpha - 1 - \alpha \log \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0^\alpha} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where the first equality is specified in arguments $\psi(\phi, \xi)$, whereas in the last equality a change in arguments has been made using the compaction strain ϵ and the elastic wetting strain ϵ^p , which is at hand for the numerical implementation. Moreover, we also introduced the ratio $\epsilon = \phi/\phi_0$ formulated in arguments $\epsilon(\epsilon, \epsilon^p)$ as

$$\epsilon = \frac{e^{\epsilon^p} - \phi_0}{e^\epsilon(1 - \phi_0) - \phi_0(1 - e^{\epsilon^p})}. \quad (18)$$

Straightforward application of equations (16) yields the fluid pressures p (relative to the configurational pressure p_0) as

$$p = p_0(\epsilon^\alpha - 1). \quad (19)$$

In view of the equation (16) we obtain in compliance form, the compaction as a function of the wetting and the fluid pressure, [8], read as

$$e^\epsilon = \frac{\left(\frac{p_0 + p}{p_0}\right)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha}} (e^{\epsilon p} - \phi_0) + (1 - e^{\epsilon p})\phi_0}{1 - \phi_0}. \quad (20)$$

And considering the rate form we obtain

$$e^\epsilon \dot{\epsilon} = - \frac{e^{\epsilon p} - \phi_0}{\alpha(p+p_0)(1-\phi_0)} \left(\frac{p+p_0}{p_0}\right)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha}} \dot{p} - \underbrace{e^{\epsilon p} \left(\frac{(p+p_0)^{-1/\alpha} - \phi_0}{1-\phi_0}\right) \frac{p}{\mu}}_{g(p,\epsilon p)p}, \quad (21)$$

where it was used that the wetting is a diffusive process represented by the viscous evolution

$$\dot{\epsilon} p = -\frac{p}{\mu}. \quad (22)$$

The parameter μ represents the viscous resistance for penetration of liquid into the bulk fibers, which is defined as

$$\mu = \frac{\nu(1 - \phi_0)\zeta^2}{K_{mes}}, \quad (23)$$

where ν is the fluid viscosity and ζ is the wetting length. The microscopic permeability K_{mes} for fiber plies is calculated based on the Gebart equation [10] for hexagonal fiber packing as

$$K_{mes} = \frac{16r^2}{9\pi\sqrt{2}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\phi_0\sqrt{3}}} - 1 \right]^{\frac{5}{2}}. \quad (24)$$

The last contribution $D^i \geq 0$ of (11) represents dissipation induced by “drag”-interaction between the phases. To accommodate this dissipation, the effective drag force \mathbf{h}_e^f (or hydraulic gradient with negative sign) is chosen to ensure positive dissipation via Darcy’s law

$$\mathbf{v}^d = -\frac{1}{\nu} \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{h}_e^f, \quad \mathbf{h}_e^f = \nabla p, \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the anisotropic permeability tensor. In order to derive the permeability for the considered VBO prepreg, a special model was developed by Rouhi et. al [11] to account for (i) the macroscopic flow between the layers and (ii) the infiltration flow into the dry (mesoscopic) fiber plies as

$$\mathbf{v}^d = -\frac{1}{\nu} \left((K_{fB}(1 - \phi^l) + K_{Ch}\phi^l)(\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{M}) + K_{fB}\mathbf{M} \right) \cdot \mathbf{h}_e^f, \quad (26)$$

where K_{fB} is the permeability through the fiber, K_{Ch} is the permeability through the channel and ϕ^l is liquid volume fraction and $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{T} \otimes \mathbf{T}$ is the plane perpendicular to the director field \mathbf{T} , cf. Fig.1. The permeability through the fiber bed K_{fB} is represented using the Gebart equation (24). The permeability through the channel may be approximated considering the resistance to viscous flow within a rectangular channel, cf. Fig.2. [11].

$$K_{Ch} = \frac{(H_0\lambda_{\parallel} - h_0^s)^2}{12}. \quad (27)$$

where λ_{\parallel} is the stretch in the direction of \mathbf{T} , H_0 is the half length of the initial fiber ply, h_0^s is the initial length of fiber bed and h_0^f is the half of the initial length of the channel through the plies.

3 Numerical procedures

3.1 Finite element approximations

In this section we outline the finite element representation of the involved primary fields and governing equations of momentum and mass balance along the corresponding constitutive equations that are used in this model development. [9]

The primary variables for the coupled mass and momentum balances are identified as the solid placement field $\mathbf{x} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}[\mathbf{X}]$ of solid particles, where a finite element subdivision of the domain is made. It is assumed that each element has the interpolation

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} N^I[\mathbf{X}] \boldsymbol{\varphi}^I = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_u^e \hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}}_e \rightarrow \mathbf{w} = \delta \boldsymbol{\varphi} = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} N^I[\mathbf{X}] \mathbf{w}^I = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_u^e \hat{\mathbf{w}}_e \quad (28)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_u^e$ contains the element shape functions and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}}_e$ is the vector element nodal placements. We obtain the spatial velocity gradient as

$$\mathbf{l} = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} \mathbf{v}^I \otimes \mathbf{g}^I, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} \mathbf{v}^I \cdot \mathbf{g}^I \quad (29)$$

where

$$\mathbf{g}^I = \mathbf{G}^I \cdot \mathbf{F}^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{G}^I = \frac{\partial N^I}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \quad (30)$$

where $N^I[\mathbf{X}]$ are the element interpolation functions and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}^I$ are the corresponding element nodal

placements. Pertinent to the Voigt matrix format, we order the components of the spatial velocity gradient as $\hat{\mathbf{l}} = \{\mathbf{l}_{11}, \mathbf{l}_{22}, \mathbf{l}_{33}, \mathbf{l}_{12}, \mathbf{l}_{21}\}^t$, and we let $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_e$ be the vector of element nodal velocities so that (29) defines the Voigt matrix representation $\hat{\mathbf{l}} = \mathbf{B}_u \delta \hat{\mathbf{v}}_e$ where \mathbf{B}_u is the strain-displacement matrix.

Likewise, the fluid pressure field is approximated, i.e. it is assumed that each element has the interpolation

$$p = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} N^I[\mathbf{X}]p^I = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_p^e \hat{\mathbf{p}}_e \rightarrow \eta = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} N^I[\mathbf{X}]\eta^I = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_p^I \hat{\eta}_e \quad (31)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_e$ is the vector nodal pressures. We thus obtain pressure gradient as $\nabla p = \mathbf{B}_p \hat{\mathbf{p}}_e$, where \mathbf{B}_p is the consequent pressure gradient interpolation matrix. The rate of pressure relative to the solid reference configuration is defined by

$$q = \dot{p} = \sum_{I=1}^{NODE} N^I[\mathbf{X}]q^I = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_p^e \hat{q}_e \quad (32)$$

whereby the integrated nodal displacement $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ and nodal pressure $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ may be assessed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}} = {}^n \hat{\mathbf{u}} + \Delta t \hat{\mathbf{v}} \quad , \quad \hat{\mathbf{p}} = {}^n \hat{\mathbf{p}} + \Delta t \hat{q} \quad (33)$$

3.2 Finite element equations

Now we can establish the set of discretized finite element equations pertinent to the present choice of interpolation of displacements and fluid pressure. In view of the weak form of momentum and mass balances in equation (9) and (10) we obtain

$$[\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}^t, \delta \hat{\mathbf{p}}^t] \bigwedge_{e=1}^{NEL} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_e - \mathbf{f}_e^{ext} \\ \mathbf{c}_e \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (34)$$

where explicit expressions for the unbalances $\mathbf{b}_e - \mathbf{f}_e^{ext}$ and \mathbf{c}_e are obtained as

$$\mathbf{b}_e - \mathbf{f}_e^{ext} = \int_{B_{0e}} (\mathbf{B}_u^e)^t (\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}} - Jp\hat{\mathbf{l}}) dV + \int_{\Gamma_e} \bar{p} (\hat{\mathbf{N}}_u^t) \mathbf{n}[s] ds \quad (35)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_e = \int_{B_{0e}} J \left((\hat{\mathbf{N}}_p^e)^t (\mathbf{1} : \mathbf{l} - n_0^\delta e^\epsilon \dot{\epsilon} - (\mathbf{B}_p^e)^t \mathbf{v}^d) \right) + \int_{\Gamma_e} (\hat{\mathbf{N}}_p^e)^t Q d\Gamma \quad (36)$$

where \bar{p} denotes the prescribed pressure on the external boundary.

The Newton iteration procedure for balancing the FE-discretized nodal forces in above equations is outlined as follow:

Given the FE-nodal velocities $\{\hat{\mathbf{v}}^{(i)}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(i)}\}$ from the iteration i , we compute the improved solution $\{\hat{\mathbf{v}}^{(i+1)}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(i+1)}\}$ as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{v}}^{(i+1)} \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(i+1)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{v}}^{(i)} \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(i)} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\xi}_v \\ \hat{\xi}_q \end{pmatrix} \quad (37)$$

where the iterative improvements $\{\hat{\xi}_u, \hat{\xi}_p\}$ are solved from the consistent linearization of equation (33) and (34), i.e.

$$[\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}^t, \delta \hat{\mathbf{p}}^t] \bigwedge_{e=1}^{NEL} \left[\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{b}_e - \mathbf{f}_e^{ext} \\ \mathbf{c}_e \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{11}^e & \mathbf{K}_{12}^e \\ \mathbf{K}_{21}^e & \mathbf{K}_{22}^e \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\xi}_v \\ \hat{\xi}_q \end{pmatrix} \right] = 0 \quad (38)$$

4 Numerical examples

To be able to test the framework numerically and see the convergence of the proposed algorithm we consider a typical compression test applied to a fluid filled fiber network, which is related to press forming of prepregs. The assumptions that have been used for the model, as they were discussed earlier, are, in short, the hyper-elastic effective stress response and the anisotropic permeability model to model the macroscopic Darcian resin flow. The involved material parameters represent a system of fiber bundles of carbon fiber and epoxy resin. [8]

To this end, the permeability parameter K_{mac} , the distance between fiber layers is $h = 20 \times 10^{-6}$, and the initial particle volume fraction is $\phi_0^p = 0.48$. As to the mechanical fiber bed response, the shear modulus is $G = 50 \times 10^6$ Pa, $k^s E = 150 \times 10^2$ Pa and the packing exponent of the fiber bed is $\beta = 4.5$. Moreover, for the micro infiltration, the liquid viscosity is chosen as $\nu = 100$ Pa · s, the initial unsaturated porosity is $n_0 = 0.85$, and the initial fiber content fraction is $\phi_0 = 0.55$. The wetting length is $\zeta = 50 \times 10^{-6}$ m, the fiber radius is $r = 3.5 \times 10^{-6}$ m, the kE -factor is $kE = 500 \times 10^6$ Pa, and the exponent of the microscopic packing exponent is $\alpha = 14.5$.

The analyzed planar specimen is shown in Fig. 3 along with the applied loading consisting of a prescribed vertical displacement r on the top boundary and fixed displacements on the lower boundary of the plate. As to the fluid pressure boundary conditions two different types are considered. The first case corresponds to macroscopically un-drained conditions, where all outer boundaries are considered impermeable. The second case is the partly drained condition, corresponding to drainage along the vertical boundaries of the specimen, where the fluid pressure is prescribed to zero. The compression test which is modeled by prescribed displacement, cf. Fig.3., is considered as a controlled displacement on the top boundary where different loading rates are considered up to the total compression, i.e. 20 percent of the height of the specimen. The relaxation is then considered by removing the load.

The results from the initial loading-relaxation test are discussed in terms of the temporal evolution of the global saturation degree measure $\langle \xi \rangle$, defined as the volume average of the saturation degrees within all elements of the mesh. Relaxation of the specimen is considered as the temporal variation of the reaction force R due to the applied loading is also shown in Fig. 4.

From the results shown in Fig.4. one can observe the process time in case of the time needed to reach the desired compaction before unloading, which is much smaller than the total time to reach the relaxation stage; the initial loading step time is around 0.01 s while the total simulation time to reach to stable level is around 0.1 s. The numerical routine is also sensitive to time.

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Fig.1. Flow channel with orientation T and fiber bed stacks

Fig.2. Distance between fiber layers and flow channel

Fig.3. The analyzed geometry.

Fig.4. Typical results from the analysis.